

Degenerate Eigenvalues - A Method to Design Adaptive Discrete Time Wavelets

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new method for designing dyadic filter banks with optimum coding gain. We conjecture that in the generic case, the optimum impulse response is the maximum eigenvector of a certain Toeplitz matrix which is maximally degenerated, which ensures that the maximum eigenvector of the Toeplitz matrix has maximum possible multiplicity. We derive analytically the optimum FIR filter of order $N = 6$, whereas closed form solutions have been available only up to order $N = 4$.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper introduces a new method for the maximization of the coding gain of dyadic filter banks. The optimization problem amounts to finding the impulse response h of a FIR filter such that the cost function $F(h) = h^T R h$ reaches a global extremum (either maximum or minimum) over the compact domain described by the Nyquist[2] restrictions.

In the absence of Nyquist constraints, the impulse response h maximizing (minimizing) $F(h) = h^T R h$ is well known to be the eigenvector corresponding to the maximum (minimum) eigenvalue of the input correlation matrix. For filterbanks a similar simple description of the optimum FIR filter was missing, despite the existence of many elegant (in general iterative) methods providing optimal or suboptimal solutions.

We conjecture here a simple and intuitive description of the optimum impulse response h :

Conjecture: Denote R' the Toeplitz matrix obtained from the input correlation matrix R by replacing the values r_{2k} (on the odd diagonals) with free parameters α_k , $k = 1, 2, \dots$. Then, in the generic case, the optimum impulse response h is the maximum eigenvector of the Toeplitz matrix R' which is maximally degenerated (corresponding to those parameters $\{\alpha_k\}_k$ which ensure that the maximum eigen-

vector of the Toeplitz matrix has maximum possible multiplicity).

In an overwhelming majority of the extensive simulations with AR input processes we found our conjecture holding true. What is therefore needed to add to our conjecture formulation in order to transform it into a theorem is the precise description of the “non-generic” conditions when it fails to hold.

Under this conjecture we are able to present in this paper closed form formulae for the optimal coding gain filter h when $N = \dim(h) = 6$. We note that closed form formulae have been presented before [6], [7], only for the case $N = \dim(h) = 4$.

The rationale behind our conjecture is detailed below. In our method we reformulate the cost function to account for the constraints via Lagrange multipliers $\{\alpha'_k\}_k$. Hence the extremum vector h has to satisfy in the first place the Nyquist constraints, and furthermore, to be the maximum eigenvector of the Toeplitz matrix R' defined above, where $\alpha_k = r_{2k} - \alpha'_k/2$.

Our main observation is that the maximum (minimum) eigenvalue of the matrix R' has to be degenerated with maximum possible multiplicity. Some specific properties of Toeplitz symmetric matrices allow us to halve the order of the involved system of equations and, moreover, to construct a set of orthonormal eigenvectors that span the subspace where lies the solution. If exists, the solution (a Nyquist[2] eigenvector, referred to as discrete time wavelet), is expressed as a linear combination of the orthonormal eigenvectors and the problem which remains to be solved is to determine the corresponding coefficients.

Our method for describing and computing the optimal coding gain filterbanks by means of maximally degenerated eigenvalues of correlation Toeplitz matrix (modified to account for Lagrange multipliers) is certainly a viable solution for short FIR filters.

2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Notations:

- h , $h^\perp$ - the FIR of a Nyquist[2] filter and its QMF

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pair: $h^\perp[n] = (-1)^{n-1}h[1-n]$, $\forall n \in \mathbb{Z}$;

- N - the filter length ($N \geq 3$); usually N is even;
- $G^{MAX}(h)$ - the maximum coding gain for a given h ;
- δ_0 - the unit impulse centered in 0;
- $\{r_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ - the autocovariance sequence of the original signal;
- $Ts[\cdot]$ - operator that constructs the Toeplitz symmetric matrix, starting from the argument;
- $R_N = Ts[r_0 \ r_1 \ \dots \ r_{N-1}]$ - the autocovariance matrix;

The optimization problem is:

$$\begin{cases} \max_{h \in \mathbb{R}^N} G^{MAX}(h) \\ \text{s.t.: } \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} h[n]h[n-2k] = \delta_0[k], \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{Z}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

It is necessary to simplify the cost function, otherwise the computations become very complex. Some well known manipulations lead to:

$$\begin{cases} \min_{h \in \mathbb{R}^N} h^T R_N(x) h \\ \text{s.t.: } h^T A_N[k] h = \delta_0[k], \quad \forall k \in \overline{0, K}. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Here: $A_N[k]$ is the power $2k$ of the compaignon matrix (nilpotent), associated to the null polynomial (for $k \in \overline{1, K}$), $A_N[0] = I_N$ (the unit matrix) and $K = \lfloor (N-1)/2 \rfloor$.

As it will be shown, when the problem is solved, if one optimum (max/min) is reached, the opposite optimum (min/max) is exactly the difference between $2r_0$ and the actual optimum, whereas the corresponding impulse responses are exactly h and $h^\perp$. The cost function in (2) being quadratic and non negative, we prefer to work with min instead of max.

3 GENERAL SOLVING STRATEGY

Starting from (2), the associated Lagrange cost function is:

$$F(h, \alpha) = h^T R_N(x) h - \lambda_0 (h^T h - 1) - \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha'_k h^T A_N[k] h, \quad (3)$$

where the multipliers are folded in $\alpha' \in \mathbb{R}^{K+1}$, beginning with λ_0 .

Equating the gradient $\nabla_{\alpha'} F$ to zero simply gives the Nyquist constraints. But equating to zero the other gradient, $\nabla_h F$, leads to the system:

$$R_N(\alpha) h = \lambda_0 h, \quad (4)$$

where we refer to $R_N(\alpha)$ as *the dashed autocovariance matrix* (Toeplitz symmetric):

$$R_N(\alpha) = Ts[r_0 \ r_1 \ \alpha_1 \ r_3 \ \alpha_2 \ r_5 \ \dots] \quad (5)$$

and $\alpha_k = r_{2k} - \alpha'_k/2$.

Thus, (4) is the *parametric spectral equation* (pse) associated to the optimization problem (2). Now, the problem is to solve the pse (4), which for every $\{\alpha_k\}_{k \in \overline{1, K}}$, is given by λ_0 and h which are eigenvalues and corresponding eigenvectors of $R_N(\alpha)$. The solution of pse, h , (if exists) must also satisfy the $(K+1)$ Nyquist[2] restrictions. That means h must have at least $(K+1)$ freedom degrees as eigenvector of λ_0 . This can be achieved if λ_0 has the multiplicity at least $(K+1)$, i.e. it is *degenerated* at least of order $(K+1)$. Moreover, if (h, α) is a solution of the pse and h verifies the constraints, then the optimum value of the initial cost function is exactly λ_0 . This proves that λ_0 must be the minimum (or the maximum) eigenvalue in the range $(0, 2r_0)$, of multiplicity at least $(K+1)$.

Two important properties of dashed matrix are useful here. Let $R \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ be a Toeplitz symmetric matrix. Then, the results below hold.

Theorem 1

Consider λ an eigenvalue of R , with the multiplicity $m \in \overline{1, N}$. Then one can construct m (or $(K+1)$ if $m > K+1$) orthonormal eigenvectors associated to λ , expressed as follows:

$$v = \begin{cases} N \text{ is even} & N \text{ is odd} \\ \left[v_0^T \mid \pm \tilde{v}_0^T \right]^T & v = \left[v_0^T \mid v_1 \mid \pm \tilde{v}_0^T \right]^T \end{cases}$$

where $v_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{\lfloor \frac{N}{2} \rfloor}$ and v_1 is a scalar.

Theorem 2

If N is even (that is $N = 2(K+1)$), then R can be split into four equivalent blocks as follows:

$$R = \begin{bmatrix} R_0 & R_1 \\ R_1^T & R_0 \end{bmatrix},$$

and: $\det(R - \lambda I_N) =$

$$= \det(R_0 + R_1 T_+ - \lambda I_{K+1}) \det(R_0 - R_1 T_+ - \lambda I_{K+1}),$$

where T_+ is the reverting operator.

These properties allow us to conceive a general strategy to solve the spe. There are three stages:

1. Searching for the minimum eigenvalue of spe, with the degenerating order at least $(K+1)$.
2. Constructing $(K+1)$ orthonormal eigenvectors as in Theorem 1.
3. Constructing the eigenvector h as a linear combination of the eigenvectors above, such that Nyquist[2] conditions be verified.

4 CASE N=6

The strategy described above can be completed in a closed form for the cases $N \in \overline{3,6}$. The cases $N \in \{3,4\}$ were previously presented [5], [6], [7], (involving different methods) and $N = 5$ is odd and therefore similar to the case $N = 6$. Hence we develop here the closed form solution only for the case $N = 6$, by using the three design stages. The general case $N > 6$, is difficult especially because of the third stage, but can be solved with a numerical algorithm.

Consider that the dashed matrix (5) has been split into 4 blocks as in the Theorem 2, for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Set $\varepsilon = \pm 1$ and use the natural notation $R_{\pm} = R_0 + \varepsilon R_1 T_{\pm}$.

One starts from the following obvious statement: *The eigenvalue λ_0 of $R_6(\alpha)$ has the multiplicity 3 if and only if at least one of the matrices $(R_+ - \lambda_0 I_3)$ and $(R_- - \lambda_0 I_3)$ has unit rank.*

Many particular cases have to be treated separately for non-general relations between r_1 , r_3 and r_5 , e.g. when two of them are equal. We treat here only the general case, these 3 numbers are in general locations.

Theorem 3

Let x be a real valued solution of the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & [(r_1 - r_3)^2 - (r_3 - r_5)(r_1 - r_5)] x^2 + \\ & + 2(r_1 - r_3)^2 x + (r_1 - r_3)(r_1 - r_5) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and set:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 &= \varepsilon \frac{r_1 - xr_3}{x - 1} \\ \alpha_2 &= \varepsilon \left[\frac{(r_3 - r_5)(r_1 + \varepsilon\alpha_1)(r_3 + \varepsilon\alpha_1)}{(r_1 - r_3)(r_1 + r_3 + 2\varepsilon\alpha_1)} - r_1 \right] \\ \lambda_0 &= r_0 + \varepsilon r_1 - \varepsilon \frac{r_3 - r_5}{r_1 - r_3} (r_1 + r_3 + 2\varepsilon\alpha_1) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Then λ_0 are 3^{rd} order degenerated eigenvalues (one for each ε) of the dashed matrix $R_6(\alpha)$.

The sum of these 2 eigenvalues is $2r_0$. Moreover, λ_0 has the multiplicity 1 for $R_{\pm}$ and 2 for $R_{\mp}$.

The last remark allows us to construct analytically the 3 orthonormal eigenvectors:

$$v_i = [v_{i1} \ v_{i2} \ v_{i3} \ | \ \varepsilon_i v_{i3} \ \varepsilon_i v_{i2} \ \varepsilon_i v_{i1}]^T, \quad \forall i \in \overline{1,3}, \quad (8)$$

where: $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon$ and $\varepsilon_2 = \varepsilon_3 = -\varepsilon$. For the first vector (multiplicity 1), the manipulations are trivial. The last 2 vectors (multiplicity 2) can be expressed in spheric coordinates:

$$\begin{cases} \sqrt{2}v_{i1} &= \sin \varphi_i \sin \theta_i \\ \sqrt{2}v_{i2} &= \cos \varphi_i \sin \theta_i \\ \sqrt{2}v_{i3} &= \cos \theta_i \end{cases}, \quad \forall i \in \overline{2,3}, \quad (9)$$

where $\varphi_i \in [-\pi, +\pi]$ and $\theta_i \in [0, +\pi]$ are some unknown angles, for any $i \in \overline{2,3}$. By the orthogonality condition

$v_2 \perp v_3$, if follows:

$$\begin{cases} \text{ctg}(\varphi_3 + \psi) &= -\varepsilon \frac{\gamma_{11}^2 \gamma_{12}^2 + \gamma_{12}^2 \gamma_{31}^2 + \gamma_{31}^2 \gamma_{11}^2}{\gamma_{11}^2 \gamma_{31}^2 \text{ctg}(\varphi_2 + \psi)} \\ \text{ctg} \theta_2 &= -\frac{\gamma_{12}}{\gamma_{11} \gamma_{31}} \sqrt{\gamma_{11}^2 + \gamma_{31}^2} \sin(\varphi_2 + \psi) \\ \text{ctg} \theta_3 &= -\frac{\gamma_{12}}{\gamma_{11} \gamma_{31}} \sqrt{\gamma_{11}^2 + \gamma_{31}^2} \sin(\varphi_3 + \psi) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where: $\text{tg} \psi = \varepsilon x$, $\gamma_{ij} = r_i + \varepsilon \alpha_j$, $i \in \{1,3\}$, $j \in \{1,2\}$ and γ_{32} is never present. Moreover, φ_2 is a free parameter, usually set to 0. Notice that the eigenvectors are very sensitive to the angle signs, but it is not so difficult to set them correctly.

The orthonormality of the 3 eigenvectors is very important for the final stage. Here, it is suitable to express h as a linear combination of v_1 , v_2 and v_3 :

$$h = av_1 + bv_2 + cv_3, \quad (11)$$

where a , b and c are the new unknown parameters.

The norm condition $h^T h = 1$ is verified if these coefficients are expressed spherically too:

$$\begin{cases} a &= \sin \alpha \sin \beta \\ b &= \cos \alpha \sin \beta \\ c &= \cos \beta \end{cases}, \quad (12)$$

where: $\alpha \in [-\pi, +\pi]$ and $\beta \in [0, +\pi]$ are the new unknown parameters.

The next two restrictions are equivalent with the equations below (derived after some manipulations, where the special form of the orthonormal eigenvectors ensures many fortunate cancellations of cross terms):

$$\begin{cases} (u_{12} - u_{11})y^2 + u_{14}y + u_{13} + u_{11} \text{tg}^2 \beta = 0 \\ (u_{22} - u_{21})y^2 + u_{24}y + u_{23} + u_{21} \text{tg}^2 \beta = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

where: $y = \cos \alpha \text{tg} \beta$ and:

$$\begin{cases} u_{11} &= v_{13}(v_{11} + \varepsilon v_{12}) \\ u_{12} &= v_{23}(v_{21} - \varepsilon v_{22}) \\ u_{13} &= v_{33}(v_{31} - \varepsilon v_{32}) \\ u_{14} &= v_{23}(v_{31} - \varepsilon v_{32}) + \\ &+ v_{33}(v_{21} - \varepsilon v_{22}) \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} u_{21} &= v_{11}v_{12} \\ u_{22} &= v_{21}v_{22} \\ u_{23} &= v_{31}v_{32} \\ u_{24} &= v_{21}v_{32} + \\ &+ v_{22}v_{31} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

A rigorous analysis is necessary, in order to solve the system (13). The main idea is to eliminate the term containing only "tg²β" (the last one in every equation). This is possible if it could be extracted from one equation (say the second one, because the coefficient u_{21} has a simpler form) and inserted into the other one (the first one, in fact). The result is only a quadratic equation in y , which can be solved easily.

As in the first stage, we skip all special cases, even though they provide valid solutions. Consider, in general case, that $u_{21} \neq 0$. Then, y is a solution of the quadratic equation:

$$\begin{aligned} & (u_{12}u_{21} - u_{11}u_{22})y^2 + (u_{14}u_{21} - u_{11}u_{24})y + \\ & + (u_{13}u_{21} - u_{11}u_{23}) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

If y is real valued, then the unknown angles are expressed by:

$$\operatorname{tg} \beta = \pm \sqrt{\frac{(u_{21} - u_{22})y^2 - u_{24}y - u_{23}}{u_{21}}}, \quad \cos \alpha = \frac{y}{\operatorname{tg} \beta}, \quad (16)$$

provided that $\operatorname{tg} \beta$ is real valued as well.

The solution of the optimization problem (2) is now complete. The required pair of discrete time wavelets is $(h, h^\perp)$. It exists if and only if x (from (6)), y (from (15)) and $\operatorname{tg} \beta$ (from (16)) are real valued. Notice that these equivalent conditions are not always fulfilled, in which case our degenerate eigenvalue approach fails. The simulations have shown that with AR input signal sometimes complex valued x or y are obtained.

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The simulations were performed within the AR class of signals. The input signal is filtered and decimated using a binary filter bank, where discrete time wavelets (length 6) are computed for each node depending on the corresponding autocovariance sequence. In order to emphasize the wavelets adaptivity, the associated continuous wavelets are constructed in every node according to [1], [2], [3].

The input signal is AR type with 20 poles and its power spectral density (psd) is represented in Figure 1 together with wavelets spectra in the node 0 (the root). The wavelet father is multi-pass rather than low pass, in this case. This property is also suggested by the associated continuous wavelets (Figures 2 and 3), their shapes being similar enough.

We also note that experiments with real speech signals were also performed, our algorithm being able to find in all cases the optimal coding gain filter.

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Figure 1: Spectra of discrete time wavelets (node 0).

Figure 2: Continuous wavelet father (node 0).

Figure 3: Continuous wavelet mother (node 0).